

Fig. B.1. NGC 6642 clusters density distributions in 411321 TNG-TVP external potential. The orbital global evolution is present in two projections (X, Y) and (X, Z), *two left panels*. GC central part in local frame with the BHs (black dots), NSs (magenta dots) and with detail central area (with box size 10 pc) we present in *two right panels*. The total time of integration is 8 Gyr forward time.

Fig. B.2. Same as in Fig. B.1 for GC HP 1.

Fig. B.3. Same as in Fig. B.1 for GC NGC 6981.

Fig. B.4. Same as in Fig. B.1 for GC NGC 6681.

Fig. B.5. Same as in Fig. B.1 for GC NGC 6401.

Fig. B.6. Same as in Fig. B.1 for GC Palomar 6.